

EDUCATIONAL EFFORTS OF MUHAMMAD KORI
ABDURASHIDKHANOVA.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6841264>

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To destroy a nation, it is necessary to destroy its
culture, art, language, so that soon it will degrade itself.
Skobelovo

Nomads of the Jadid movement have gone through a difficult path of development from Enlightenment to a powerful political movement. The socio-political life in Turkestan of the late XIX-early XX centuries, the colonial policy of the tsarist empire, the difficult economic situation of the people, economic backwardness from the developed countries of the world, cultural backwardness, stagnation in the public consciousness were an important impetus to national consciousness, the growth of Jadidism. They understood perfectly well that progressives armed insurrection is useless to rebel, that oppressed people can be united with enlightenment with the help of values such as freedom, freedom, humiliation.

The head of this historic mission was the head of the Tashkent Jadids Munavvarkori Abdurashidkhanov. He not only opened a Jadid school and a Jadid newspaper in Tashkent, but also in 1913 laid the foundation of one of the first central organizations in Turkestan - the Turan Society, and in 1917 - the Shuroi Islamia society on Turan land. Soon, by the will of the historical period, with his direct participation, the organization "Turkic man centriyat" was created. According to the information provided by munavvarkori Abdurashidkhanov, in 1919, a nationwide Kurultai "Ittihad va Tarkki" was held in one of the parks near the Kashkar mahalla of Tashkent, on which the foundation of the organization "Milliy Ittihad" was laid [1].

According to our Jadids, they knew that for the development of the Motherland and the nation, it is necessary to study not only religious sciences, but also secular ones. Mahmudhoja Behbudi said, "O Muslims! Teach your children the science of the future! After all, Allah Almighty has made them popular, except for your time, that is, for the time to come," [2] - This is proof of this.

Munavvarkori also held the same view. To this end, in 190, he was one of the first in Tashkent to open a new school. More importantly, according to

Mahmudhoji Behbudi, the prestige of the Munavvarkori school was high and could lay the foundation for higher education. This school, opened in Shaikhantakhur, was called "Exemplary" and played a special role in updating teaching methods. Munavvar Kari himself was the editor of the newspaper "Turkestan Vedomosti" G. In his dialogue with Andreev, he said that this was what he wanted from the school:

"I came up with the idea to find a good way that could quickly, easily and easily lead those who have been studying in madrasas for years. I wanted to create a small school, a madrasah based on a new applied, fundamental modern pedagogy"[3].

Munavvarkori compiled such manuals for these schools as "adibi avval", "Adibi Sony", "Yer Zizi". Professor begali Kasimov found that these textbooks were published separately in the period from 1901 to 1917, at least two or three times, and most-from nine to ten times [4].

In 1925, in collaboration with Munavvarkori, Kayyum Ramazan and Shorasul Zunnun, he published a three-volume book "Lessons of the Uzbek language". All this suggests that for Munavvarkori, one of the ranks of Turkestan Jadidism, it was vitally important to increase the enlightenment of the nation, to update teaching methods for this, to invest in the education of the generation. It is no coincidence that the main goal of the Jadids was to bring Turkestan, backward in the development of the country, to the level of developed mamalakats. Therefore, it was necessary to send young people to study in developing countries, to lay the foundation for the future. It shouldn't have happened on its own. On May 1909, 12, Tashkent Jadids opened the Jamiyat Hai charitable foundation. Munavvarkori was one of his sons. In the activities of this charitable society, special attention was paid to education. In particular, the methods created for the youth of Turkestan were taken into account, from supporting the activities of Jadid schools to sending them to foreign advanced educational institutions for higher education[5].

1918, April 9, he begins work on the creation of the Muslim people's dorulfun, that is, the National University, in the courtyard of which a life of 9 people will be created in Darkhan. All of them unanimously confirm the important role of the university in the life of the nation. Soon the newspaper began to be published under the name "Hulk dorulfuni". From the "report of the Organizational Commission" published in the newspaper on May 31, June 15, July 21, 1918, it became known that from April 9 to May 9, 1918, 9 meetings were held at Roppa Rossa. At these meetings, the organizational structures of the future university were developed-from branches, faculties to programs of the most important areas of activity.

According to them, the university was divided into 3 levels: lower, middle and higher. Special attention was paid to foreign languages. From the West,

it is mandatory to study German, English, French, and from the East-Arabic, Persian. Thus, on May 1918, 12, the Turkestan Muslim People's House was opened in the old city part of Tashkent under the leadership of Munavvarkori Abdurashidkhanov. As a truly national university, it has become an important event in the spiritual life of the region. This is evidenced by the fact that on the opening day of the university, the number of people wishing to study there reached 945 people. On May 15, the charter of the university was adopted. Professor B. Kasimov writes: "In a short period of time, 23 schools were created, 299 teachers were involved. Of these, 23 people graduated from higher religious madrassas, 2 from Russian universities"[6].

In conclusion, we can say that our students knew that in order for the fate of the Motherland, the people and the country of tomorrow, it is necessary to start acting from today. History shows that Mana in kori Abdurashidkhanov, despite the resistance, continued to fight, understood that it was not worth stopping there, conducted his activities, considering the fate of the Motherland. Currently, we, as the younger generation, do not get tired of learning, extracting the necessary lessons from it.

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